

Exploring multidisciplinary working to prevent homelessness: findings from an evaluation of an integrated housing/health service

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Introduction

Homelessness is a major and costly public health problem with wide ranging impacts on individuals, communities and the wider health care system. Recent policy attention in the UK has focused on the need for the integration of services to prevent homelessness. Here we present findings from an evaluation of an integrated service which aims to support individuals experiencing multiple complex to access services and prevent repeat homelessness.

Methods

The evaluation adopted a mixed methods study design. We utilised interviews with service users (N=9), professionals across the housing and health system (N=17), over 30 hours of observation data from key meetings and analysis of routine data (N=97). The evaluation was underpinned by a coproduction and action research approach whereby findings were used to inform local delivery and the intervention progressed.

Findings

Service users were positive about the support which facilitated access to a range of support services including GPs and support with debt and money management. Practitioners felt that the alliance agreement supported data sharing and created accountability for support actions across the system. However, several challenges in delivering multidisciplinary support emerged from the evaluation including a lack of consistent representation from health partners which impeded prevention work, a perceived duplication of support and misunderstandings of the remit of the service.

Conclusion

The importance of multidisciplinary working was evident across the evaluation. The service is an important part of the system but can't do this alone and requires consistent engagement from health and housing partners for successful implementation.